

BACTERIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF SACHET WATER VENDED IN UGBOR, BENIN CITY, NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

Sachet water is the ultimate source of drinking water in Nigeria. Twelve brands of sachet water vended in Ugbor village, Oredo Local Government Area, Benin City were analysed to determine the sensory properties, pH and the bacteriological quality using standard methods. Antibiotic susceptibility profile of the bacteria isolates was carried out using the disc diffusion method. All the samples were clear and odourless. The pH readings of the water samples ranged between 5.0 and 7.2. Bacterial growths were recorded in eleven out of the twelve water samples. The total heterotrophic count was between $2.2 - 8.9 \times 10^1$ cfu/ml. Coliforms were present in six of the water samples with a count of $2.2 - 4.3 \times 10^1$ cfu/ml. The isolates were identified as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas* sp, *Aeromonas* sp, *Corynebacterium* sp, *Bacillus* sp, *Bacillus badius*, *Proteus vulgaris* and *Escherichia coli*. *Staphylococcus aureus* had the highest percentage occurrence of 24% while *Bacillus* sp., *Escherichia coli* and *Corynebacterium* sp. had the lowest percentage occurrence of 8% each. It was observed that all of the isolates were resistant to Ceftazidime (caz), Cefuroxime (crx), and Augmentin (aug) and sensitive to Ciprofloxacin (cpr) and Ofloxacin (ofl). Most of the isolates were sensitive to Gentamicin (gen) except for *Pseudomonas* sp., *Escherichia coli*, and *Proteus vulgaris*. Most of the isolates were resistant to Cefixime (cxm) except for *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Corynebacterium* sp. and *Bacillus badius*. Eleven of the twelve sachet water samples studied did not meet WHO standard for drinking water, hence, routine monitoring of producers of sachet water should be enforced.

Keywords: Quality, Sachet water, Ugbor, Edo state, pH, Antibiotics, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Aeromonas* sp, *Escherichia coli*

INTRODUCTION

The safety of drinking water is a worldwide public health concern. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimated that 1.1 billion of the world's population does not have access to safe water. In addition, 80 percent of diseases and one-third of deaths in developing countries are due to consumption of contaminated water (WHO, 2011). In Nigeria, it is reported that the incidence of acute watery diarrhoea is approximately 4.9 episodes per year and there are approximately 200,000 diarrhoea related deaths of children aged below five years with an average of 300 deaths per day (United Nations, 2012). Great concern must therefore be given to

the quality of drinking water which is very critical in maintaining good health and for the overall socio-economic development of any society.

Due to the scarcity of safe drinking water in Nigeria, communities obtain their potable water in form of sachet water, popularly referred to as 'pure water'. It is the most common source of drinking water in Nigeria, given that it is relatively cheap, accessible and generally perceived to be of better quality (Stoler, 2012). Drinking water industries in Nigeria, mostly owned by private institutions obtain water from surface or underground sources and since both types of water can become contaminated by biological and chemical pollutants originating from point and nonpoint sources, it is usually followed by various treatment processes.

Bacterial growth in drinking water depends on concentration of assimilated organic carbon, limiting nutrients, disinfectant concentration, type of pipe material, packaging nylons and a number of other factors such as; pH, temperature, hardness, redox potential that controls the growth of microorganisms on pipe surfaces (Lehtola *et al.*, 2002; Ollos *et al.*, 2003). Many of the bacteria isolated in water distribution systems are opportunistic pathogens. The presence of high numbers of opportunistic pathogens in drinking water is of concern because these microorganisms can lead to infection of certain segments of the population (newborn babies, the sick, and the elderly) (Bitton, 2005).

According to the guideline set by the World Health Organisation, quality drinking water must not contain *Escherichia coli* or thermotolerant coliform bacteria, giardia worms, viruses, *Cryptosporidium* spp, *Legionella pneumophila*, *Entamoeba histolytica* and other opportunistic pathogens such as *Clostridium* sp., *Klebsiella* sp. and *Pseudomonas* (WHO, 2011). The guideline further stated that the water should be tested against the presence of highly virulent pathogens such as *Salmonella typhi*, *Shigella dysenteriae* and *Vibrio cholerae* that are responsible for typhoid, bacillary dysentery and cholera diseases respectively which arises due to high level of organic decay and fermentation on tropical waters. All these bacteria must not exist in water that are meant for drinking, hence, sources of water for packaged water are subjected to laboratory test by public analyst in which any of the bacteria must not be found or detected in any 100ml water sample.

Various studies carried out on sachet water from different cities have revealed the lack of purity of sachet drinking water in Nigeria (Oladipo *et al.*, 2009; Afiukwa *et al.*, 2010; Edema *et al.*, 2011; Akpoborie, and Ehwarimo, 2012; Onilude *et al.*, 2013). This is attributed to sharp practices, poor hygiene of vendors, polluted environment, and non-adherence to WHO/NAFDAC regulations (Omalu *et al.*, 2010). It is therefore imperative that the quality of sachet water vended be continuously assessed for the protection of public health.

Also, the spread of resistance to antibiotics makes water borne infections difficult to treat. Antibiotics act on microorganisms by inhibiting peptidoglycan synthesis, protein synthesis, and

nucleic acid synthesis (interruption of nucleotide metabolism, inhibition of RNA polymerase or DNA gyrase) or by affecting the cell membrane integrity (Russel, 2002). Increased use of antibiotics is often associated with increased resistance of bacteria to these chemicals, especially in the hospital setting (Swartz, 1997). The aim and objectives of this research, therefore, is to isolate and characterize bacteria from different sachet water sold in Ugbor Area, Benin City, Nigeria and to determine the antibiotic susceptibility profile of the bacteria isolates.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

MATERIALS

Collection of samples

A total of twelve sachet water samples of different brands were bought from the vendors in Ugbor Area, Benin City and taken to the laboratory for analysis. The samples were coded as NES, AVE, JAB, ACT, SIM, VAS, OLI, MON, NOT, VEO, LAG and UNI to reflect the respective brands.

Physical parameters

Sensory analysis was carried out on the sachet water samples to determine the odour and general appearance. The pH of each water sample was also checked using a pH meter (Jenway, 3510)

Culture media

The culture media used include Nutrient agar (Oxoid) to determine the total viable bacterial count, Eosin Methylene Blue agar (LAB M) to enumerate *Escherichia coli*, MacConkey agar (Oxoid) for coliform count and Salmonella-Shigella agar for the determination of *Salmonella* and *Shigella* counts. Culture media were all prepared according to the respective Manufacturers' specification and sterilized in an autoclave at 121°C at 15 psi for 15 minutes.

Enumeration and isolation of bacteria

A 1 ml aliquot of each water sample was inoculated aseptically on each of the sterilized agar using the pour-plate method. The plates were incubated for 24 h at 37°C, after which visible colonies were counted and expressed in cfu/ml. Distinct colonies were selected and purified by repeated streaking on Nutrient agar plates. Pure cultures were preserved on agar slants at 5°C and renewed at 2-weekly intervals.

Characterization and identification of isolates

Morphological characterization

The colony of the pure cultures of each bacterial isolates was observed for morphological features using Bergey's Manual of Determinative Bacteriology. Cell shape was determined under

X100 objective of the light microscope after Gram staining procedure. Gram staining was carried out as described by Olutiola *et al.* (1991).

Biochemical characterization

This was carried out according to standard techniques described by Olutiola *et al.* (1991). Biochemical tests carried out include; Oxidase test, Indole test, Urease test, Methyl red test, Voges Proskauer and tests for the fermentation of different sugars. Bacterial isolates were identified using Bergey's Manual of Determinative Bacteriology.

Identification of isolates

The isolates were identified using Bergey's Manual of Determinative Bacteriology. (Buchanan and Gibbon, 1974).

Antibiotic susceptibility test

The antibiotic sensitivity pattern of the isolates was determined using the disc diffusion method (Harley and Prescott, 2002). Nutrient agar plates were prepared and appropriately labelled. The plates were seeded with the standardized bacterial cultures by spread plate technique. The inoculated plates were left to dry for 15 mins. Commercially available antibiotics disc containing varying concentration of various types of antibiotics were placed at adequate distances on each of the seeded agar plates with the aid of sterile forceps under aseptic conditions. The antibiotics disc were; Cefotaxime (ctx) (30 μ g), Cefuroxime (crx) (30 μ g), Gentamicin (Gen) (10 μ g), Cefixime (cxm) (5 μ g), Ofloxacin (ofl) (5 μ), Augmentin (aug) (30 μ), Nitrofurantoin (Nit) (300 μ g) and Ciprofloxacin (cpr) (5 μ g). The plates were incubated for 24 hours at 37°C. The resultant visible zones of inhibition were measured in millimeters (mm). Distance lesser than 14 mm were regarded as resistant (R) while distance that ranged from 14 mm to 17 mm were indicated as intermediate (I). Also, zones of inhibition greater than 17mm were recorded as susceptible (S) (Harley and Prescott, 2002).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RESULTS

Table 1 shows that all the water samples were odourless and clear in appearance. The pH readings of the water samples ranged between 5.0 and 7.2. Three water samples VEO, UNI and LAG with pH 6.6, 7.0 and 7.2 respectively were within the W.H.O stipulated range of 6.5 – 8.5 while the other nine water samples fell below the range.

Table 1: pH, Odour and Appearance of sachet water samples

Sample code	pH	Odour	Appearance
NES	5.8	odourless	clear
AVE	5.7	odourless	clear
JAB	6.0	odourless	clear
ACT	5.8	odourless	clear
SIM	5.0	odourless	clear
VAS	5.1	odourless	clear
OLI	5.9	odourless	clear
MON	5.5	odourless	clear
NOT	5.8	odourless	clear
VEO	6.6	odourless	clear
LAG	7.2	odourless	clear
UNI	7.0	odourless	clear

Table 2 shows the heterotrophic counts, coliform count, *Salmonella-Shigella* counts and *Escherichia coli* count of the sachet water sample. All the water samples, except sample NOT, were contaminated with bacteria. Sample water NES and LAG has the highest heterotrophic counts of 8.9×10^1 cfu/ml while samples ACT, SIM and OLI had the lowest count of 2.2×10^1 cfu/ml. Coliforms were present in six water samples (NES, JAB, ACT, AVE, LAG and UNI). NES and JAB had the highest coliform counts of 4.3×10^1 cfu/ml while ACT had the lowest mean coliform count of 2.2×10^1 cfu/ml. Samples SIM, VAS, OLI, MON, NOT and VEO were devoid of coliforms. All of the water samples were free of *Salmonella* and *Shigella*. *Escherichia coli* was present in NES and UNI with counts of 2.2×10^1 cfu/ml and 3.8×10^1 cfu/ml respectively.

Twelve brands of sachet water were analysed and a total of eight bacteria isolates were identified from eleven of the sachet water samples. The isolates were initially differentiated on the basis of the cultural and morphological studies after which they were subjected to various biochemical characterization tests. These tests revealed their probable identity as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas* sp, *Aeromonas* sp, *Corynebacterium* sp, *Bacillus* sp, *Bacillus badius*, *Proteus vulgaris* and *Escherichia coli*. as shown in table 3.

Table 2: Total heterotrophic count, Salmonella-Shigella (SS) count, total coliform count and *Escherichia coli* (*E.coli*) count of sachet water samples ($\times 10^1$ cfu/ml)

Sample code	Total bacterial counts (cfu/ml)	Coliform count (cfu/ml)	Salmonella-Shigella count (cfu/ml)	<i>E.coli</i> count (cfu/ml)
NES	8.9	4.3	-	2.2
AVE	7.1	3.6	-	-
JAB	6.0	4.3	-	-
ACT	2.2	2.2	-	-
SIM	2.2	-	-	-
VAS	6.5	-	-	-
OLI	2.2	-	-	-
MON	6.4	-	-	-
NOT	-	-	-	-
VEO	6.0	-	-	-
LAG	6.0	4.0	-	-
UNI	8.9	3.8	-	3.8

KEY: - = Absent

Figure 1 depicts the percentage occurrence of the bacteria isolated from the sachet water samples. *Staphylococcus aureus* had the highest percentage occurrence of 24%, *Proteus vulgaris* 16%, *Aeromonas* sp. 13%, *Bacillus badius* 11%. *Pseudomonas* sp. had 10%, *Corynebacterium* sp. 8%, *Escherichia coli* 8%, and *Bacillus* sp. had 8% occurrence.

TABLE 3: Morphological and Biochemical characterization of bacteria isolated from the sachet water samples

Morphological and biochemical characteristics	Isolate code							
	ACT1	SIM3	LAG2	JAB1	UNI1	OLI2	UNI3	NES3
Cell form	Circular	Circular	Circular	Circular	Irregular	Circular	Circular	Circular
Colony margin	Entire	Flat	Undulate	Flat	Entire	Flat	Flat	Flat
Elevation	Convex	Flat	Flat	Flat	Flat	Flat	Convex	Flat
Pigmentation	Cream	Cream	Cream	Purple	Green metallic sheen	Cream	Cream	Pink
Optical characteristics	Opaque	Opaque	Opaque	Opaque	Opaque	Opaque	Opaque	Opaque
Gram stain	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	-
Cell shape	Cocci	Rod	Rod	Rod	Rod	Rod	Rod	Rod
Catalase	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
Oxidase	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
Indole	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	-
Urease	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Methyl red	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	+
Voges Proskauer	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Motility	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	-
SUGAR								
FERMENTATION								
Glucose	A/G	-	A/G	A/G	-	A/G	-	-
Lactose	-	A/G	A/G	-	-	A/G	-	-
Sucrose	-	-	-	-	A/G	-	-	-
Maltose	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
D-xylose	A/G	-	A/G	-	A/G	-	A/G	-
D-manitol	A	A	A	A	A/G	A/G	A/G	-
Probable organism	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>P. sp</i>	<i>A.sp</i>	<i>C. sp</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>B.badius</i>	<i>B. sp</i>	<i>P. vulgaris</i>

KEY: - = negative, + = positive, A/G = acid and gas production, A= acid production, *S. aureus*= *Staphylococcus aureus*, *P.sp*= *Pseudomonas sp*, *A.sp*= *Aeromonas sp*, *C.sp*= *Corynebacterium sp*, *E.coli*= *Escherichia coli*, *B.sp*= *Bacillus badius*, *P.vulgaris*= *Proteus vulgaris*, - = Absent

Figure 1: Percentage occurrence of bacteria isolated from Sachet water samples

Table 4 shows the zone of inhibition of the bacteria isolates to the antibiotics tested. The antibiotics disc were; Ceftazidime (caz) (30 μ g), Cefuroxime (crx) (30 μ g), Gentamicin (Gen) (10 μ g), Cefixime (cxm) (5 μ g), Ofloxacin (ofl) (5 μ), Augmentin (aug) (30 μ), Nitrofurantoin (Nit) (300 μ g) and Ciprofloxacin (cpr) (5 μ g). It was observed that all of the isolates were resistant to Ceftazidime (caz), Cefuroxime (crx), and Augmentin (aug) and sensitive to Ciprofloxacin (cpr) and Ofloxacin (ofl). Five of the isolates were sensitive to Gentamicin (gen) except for *Pseudomonas sp.*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Proteus vulgaris*. On the other hand, five of the isolates were resistant to Cefixime (cxm) except for *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Corynebacterium sp.* and *Bacillus badius*.

Table 4: Antibiotic Inhibition Spectrum of bacteria isolated from sachet water samples (zone of inhibition measured in ‘mm’)

Bacterial isolates	CPR	CAZ	CRX	GEN	CXM	OFL	AUG	NIT
<i>S. aureus</i>	24.5	R	R	14.5	12.0	23.5	R	16.5
<i>Pseudomonas sp.</i>	27.5	R	R	R	R	14.5	R	R
<i>Aeromonas sp.</i>	24.5	R	R	23.0	R	26.5	R	22.0
<i>Corynebacterium sp.</i>	27.0	R	R	14.5	14.5	28.5	R	23.5
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	21.0	R	R	R	R	23.5	R	R
<i>Bacillus badius</i>	27.0	R	R	14.5	14.5	28.5	R	23.5
<i>Bacillus sp</i>	23.5	R	R	22.5	R	23.5	R	R
<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	27.5	R	R	R	R	14.5	R	R

KEY: CPR = Ciprofloxacin, CAZ = Ceftazidime, CRX = Cefuroxime, GEN = Gentamycin, CXM = Cefixime, OFL = Ofloxacin, AUG = Augmentin, NIT = Nitrofurantoin, R= Resistant (zone diameter less than 14mm)

DISCUSSION

Natural water, either from surface or underground sources are subjected to different types of treatment based on the available resources and technologies to meet the criteria for portable water. However, water meant for dinking in many developing countries are improperly treated, hence, still fall below the WHO standard as far as physicochemical and microbiological qualities are concerned (WHO/UNICEF, 2000; WHO, 2003). Sachet water is widely taken by all sections of the population in Nigeria. Nine out of the twelve sachet-water samples analyzed in this study have pHs that fell below the WHO standard for drinking water (NAFDAC, 2004). However, they were all odourless and clear, in line with WHO requirements (NAFDAC, 2004). The pHs of respective satchet-water samples is a reflection of the environmental sources of the water and the anthropogenic activities associated with such environment. The inability of the treatment method employed to bring the pHs within the required standard may be due to process failure (Rosenberg, 2002).

Occurrence of bacteria was recorded in eleven of the sachet-water samples. The total bacterial counts were higher than what is stipulated to be acceptable for portable water (1.0×10^1 cfu/ml)

(NAFDAC, 2004). This study also showed the presence of pathogenic bacteria in 50% of the sachet water samples that were analyzed. High load of coliforms and *E. coli* were found in some of the sachet-waters. WHO standard stated that there must be no pathogenic bacteria in portable water (NAFDAC, 2004). This is an indication that the sachet-water samples are contaminated, especially with fecal materials and unsafe for drinking. The presence of relative heavy load of bacteria in water packaged for drinking purposes has been previously documented in literature (Onifade and Ilori, 2008; Oladipo *et al.*, 2009; Oyedeji *et al.*, 2010; Onilude *et al.*, 2013). Microbial contamination of treated and packaged water is due to several factors that contribute to failure of treatment process. They include poor hygienic conditions of the handlers, presence of biofilms on processing surfaces due to poor cleaning and sanitation and packaging of treated water under unhygienic conditions (Ollos *et al.*, 2003).

The bacteria characterized and identified from the sachet water samples were found mostly to be opportunistic pathogens which are usually isolated from unhygienic environments or materials (Bitton, 2005). The predominant ones include *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Pseudomonas* sp., *Bacillus* sp. and *Aeromonas* sp. Reports on studies of sachet water from different locations recorded the occurrence of these bacteria. Onifade and Ilori (2008) encountered *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* in sachet water samples vended in Ondo State. These microorganisms are versatile in their nutrient requirements and can survive with limited nutrient availability. Most of these bacteria are indigenous to aquatic environments (Berger and Oshiro, 2002). *Aeromonas* and *Pseudomonas* are well known indicators of potential bacterial regrowth in nutrient limited environments such as channels of water distribution systems (Van der Kooij, 1978; Ribas *et al.*, 2000). The ingestion of these bacteria with contaminated water constitute public health risks to the immunocompromised members of the population, especially newborn babies, elderly and sick people (LeChevallier *et al.*, 1980).

Bacterial resistance to antibiotics has been documented in a number of previous studies (Armstrong *et al.*, 1981; Yah, 2007; Pathak and Goopal, 2008; Sharma and Rai, 2012.). Patients receiving antibiotic therapy harbor a large number of antibiotic-resistant bacteria in their intestinal tract. These bacteria are excreted in large numbers in feces and eventually reach the community wastewater treatment plant. The genes coding for antibiotic resistance are often located on plasmids (R factors) and under appropriate conditions, can be transferred to other bacteria through conjugation or other modes of recombination. The high resistance pattern of all the bacteria isolates in this work could be as a result of their acquisition of antibiotic resistance. Drug-resistant pathogen cause infections that are difficult to treat (Bitton, 2005).

In conclusion, waterborne diseases pose very serious threats to society. Eleven of the twelve sachet water types studied did not meet WHO standards for drinking water, hence, routine

monitoring of producers of sachet water should be enforced to ensure adherence to drinking water standard.

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